

tillering brought about by the changes in nucleic acid metabolism in rice apexes

(see table). The LSF decreases the activity of endogenous rice gibberellins

and the silica (SiO₂) content of the straw. The latter can cause rice lodging.

Constraints to high yields

Farmers' perceptions of constraints to high yields in wetland paddy

P. B. Chatterjee, A. K. Maitra, M. K. Sarkar, and Subir Dutta, Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, Pandua, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

A study was conducted to determine farmers' perceptions of the relative contribution of socioeconomic and biologic constraints to high yields in kharif or wetland paddy. Among the biophysical constraints considered were water management, situation-specific rice varieties, weed control, insect and disease incidence, problem soils, soil fertility, and cultural management. Socioeconomic constraints were knowledge, institutional credit, absentee land-ownership, the sharecropping system, village leadership, input availability, marketing of farm produce, adequate legislation, fragmentation of holding, farming tradition, and risk aversion.

Stratified random samples were taken in 14 villages. The farmers were thoroughly briefed on the significance of the constraints and asked to rate their perceptions of each. A total of 189 marginal, small, and large farmers tilled in score sheets, which were tabulated. Score values on individual constraints were obtained by multiplying the rank marked by the farmers by the frequency. The ranking of each constraint was obtained in terms of percentage from the total rank score given by the farmers against the biophysical and socioeconomic constraints. The data are presented in the table; yield constraints (%) in kharif rice are in the figure. ■

Farmers' ranking of biophysical and socioeconomic constraints. West Bengal, India.

Constraint	All farmers' rank (n = 189)	Rank given by		
		Marginal farmers ^a (n = 139)	Small farmers ^b (n = 38)	Large farmers ^c (n = 12)
Biophysical				
Insect pests and diseases	1	1	2	2
Water management	2	2	1	1
Soil and fertility	3	3	4	3
Situation-specific rice varieties	4	4	3	4
Cultural management	5	5	5	5
Weed control	6	6	6	6
Socioeconomic				
Institutional credit	1	1	2	1
Input availability	2	2	1	2
Knowledge	3	3	4	3
Village leadership	4	4	5	4
Marketing of farm produce	5	5	3	5
Legislation safeguarding farmers' interest	6	7	6	6
Tradition	7	6	7	7
Fragmentation of landholding	8	8	8	8
Risk aversion	9	10	9	9
Absentee landowner	10	9	10	10

^a Holding as much as 1 ha of land. ^b Holding from 1 to 2 ha ^c Holding more than 2 ha.

Proportion (%) of farmers mentioning biophysical and socioeconomic constraints on kharif rice, West Bengal, India.